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Abstract

There are things learners can't easily do, such as retrieving words at speed or achieving long, pause-free runs. This is because they lack certain skills. Subsequent article will look more closely at how learners can become more skilful. But there are also things learners don't know, such as what to say in order to signal a change of topic or how to respond appropriately to a difficult request, and this also inhibits their fluency. In these cases, they lack the knowledge. This article looks at ways of helping them uncover these gaps in their knowledge.

Keywords: achieve, attention, increasing, speaker, learners, awareness

Activities aimed at helping learners uncover these gaps we will call awareness activities, rather than simply presentation activities, since the former term allows the possibility of learners discovering — and even filling — their knowledge gaps themselves. The assumption is, though, that the teacher will always be on hand to guide the process and provide support and feedback where necessary.

What exactly is awareness? The concept comes from cognitivist learning theory which argues that, as a prerequisite for the restructuring of the learner's mental representation of the language, some degree of conscious awareness is necessary. Awareness involves at least three processes: attention, noticing, and understanding.

- **Attention** - learners need to be paying attention, i.e. they need to be on the alert — interested, involved, and curious — if they are going to notice features of the target skill.

- **Noticing** — this is more than simply paying attention. While someone is driving, they can be paying attention without noticing a great deal until a kangaroo suddenly bounds onto the road. Noticing, then, is the conscious registering of the occurrence of some event or entity. Noticing is more likely if the event or entity is somehow surprising (like the kangaroo) or if it is salient because of its frequency, size, significance, or usefulness, among other things. We also notice things if they have been previously pointed out to us. Many learners, having recently been taught a new word, will be familiar with the experience of noticing it everywhere. The prior teaching has primed them to notice what before had gone unobserved. It's also possible to notice the absence of something. For example, a learner might notice a 'hole' in their language proficiency as the result of being incapable of expressing a particular idea. They can also notice the difference between their own, novice, performance and the performance of an expert. This is called noticing the gap.

- **Understanding** - finally, there is no real awareness without understanding. Understanding means the recognition of a general rule or principle or pattern. This is more likely if there are several instances of the item that is being targeted for learning, so that the pattern or rule can be more easily perceived.[1]

All these processes can be aided and supported by the presence of either a teacher or other learners. For example, the teacher can ensure a heightened degree of attention by recounting an anecdote that has a humorous or unusual outcome. She can promote noticing by incorporating into the story several instances of a narrative device, such as the sentence starter *and the X thing was...* where X can stand for *funny, odd, strange, weird* etc. Finally, she can support the learners' understanding of this pattern — both its form and its narrative function - by asking the learners to underline each instance of the pattern in a transcript of the anecdote.

Learners can also collaborate in the awareness-raising process, as when, in small groups, they jointly construct and rehearse a story based on picture prompts and then tell it to the members of another group, who have to put the pictures in order as they listen. The task prompts a degree of attention, and, in rehearsing the task, individual learners may 'notice the gap' between their performance and that of their peers. In attempting to fill the gap, they may be motivated to ask for assistance from their peers, and the assistance may take the form of an explanation, which in turn may aid understanding.

Of course, there is no guarantee that any of these processes will happen. But the activities that are outlined in the rest of this chapter attempt to provide optimal awareness-raising conditions and thereby maximize the chances that these learning processes will occur.

One way to raise learners' awareness of features of spoken language is to expose them to instances of speaking and to have them study transcripts of such instances. Traditionally this has taken the form of playing learners recordings, either of monologue or multiparty talk (i.e. talk where several speakers are interacting), which are typically pre-scripted and performed by actors. However, the lack of spontaneity that results from being both scripted and performed means that these recordings are often only superficially representative of real spoken language. They may lack such performance effects as pause fillers, back-tracking, and repair, and they seldom display the characteristics of interactive talk, such as turn-taking, in anything but a rather idealized way. This lack of

authenticity is compounded by the fact that these recordings are often designed to display a pre-selected grammar structure and are almost always simplified to ensure intelligibility. By way of an example, here are two transcripts of the speakers talking about a similar topic. One, from J Coates' book *Men Talk* is authentic — in the sense it was unscripted and spontaneous. The other is how it might appear in a coursebook.

Speaker 1. I went in and bought some stupid things this morning in Boots, twenty-five p, [laugh] for twenty-five p you could be as silly as you want to couldn't you? Silly aren't they? Oh what fun. Silly green nonsense. Children's bead earrings.

Speaker 2. You got green?

Speaker 1. I've got a green jumper which I wear in the winter

Speaker 2. Yeah that's fine

Speaker 1. So I thought I would. I'm - am very fond of my green jumper, silly pair of green earrings to go with it.

Speaker 2. Why not?

Speaker 1. It's a laugh. There was another lady there looking through all the stuff where I was and she said to me, 'Isn't it fun?' [laugh] and I said, 'Yes, only twenty-five p,' [laugh] Absurd.

Earrings 1 (authentic version)

Speaker1: Whar nice earings

Speaker 2: I bought this morning

Speaker1:Where did you buy them

Speaker 2:I bought them in boots

Speaker1: How much did they cost?

Speaker 2: only 25 p.

Speaker1: What a bargain

Speaker 2; I am going ti wear them with my green jumper

Speaker 1. What a good idea!

Earrings 2 (coursebook version)[2]

The 'coursebook' dialogue is a far remove from naturally occurring speech. Its symmetrical turn distribution between speakers and its uniform utterance length are rare in casual talk among friends, where individual speakers typically hold the floor for longer periods of time and less equitably. On the other hand, *Earrings 2* is probably a lot more intelligible to learners than *Earrings 1*. The language is simplified, the turns are short, there is more redundancy in the language (i.e. language that is not strictly necessary is repeated as in *Where did you buy them? I bought them in Boots...*), [3] and there are no asides, overlaps, interruptions, and other characteristics of unscripted talk. The authentic conversation, on the other hand, consists of a number of relatively long turns, uses ungraded language, and includes a good deal of ellipsis as well as direct reference to the immediate (unseen) situation. Because it has not been recorded in a sound studio, it is also likely to be less clearly audible than the coursebook dialogue, and thus less attractive for classroom purposes.

Pre-scripted recordings should not be dismissed totally, therefore. Apart from greater audibility, one advantage of scripting speech is that teachers can incorporate repeated examples of particular features that they want their learners to notice. For example, in

Earrings 2, there are three instances of the construction *what + noun phrase (what a bargain! etc)*, expressing surprise or approval. Although it makes the conversation sound a little artificial, there is more chance that the construction will be noticed here than in the first, authentic conversation, where the same construction is much less salient.

As a compromise, scripted conversations could attempt to take into account, and to incorporate, features of naturally-occurring spoken language without sacrificing their pedagogic utility. Here is a reworked version of the earrings conversation, for example:

Speaker 1: What nice earrings!

Speaker 2: Do you like them? Silly, aren't they? Silly green nonsense. I bought them in Boots this morning. Twenty-five p.

Speaker 1: What a bargain! Have you got something green to go with them?

Speaker 2: I've got a green jumper which I wear in the winter. So I thought I'd get some silly green earrings to go with it.

Speaker 1: Whatfun!

Speaker 2: I know. It's a laugh. Only twenty-five p!

Earrings 3

One problem with both the authentic and non-authentic recordings that are commercially available is that they are almost exclusively of native speakers talking. It is arguable that exposure to only native speakers sets a Standard of spoken interaction that is beyond either the means or the needs of most learners and that it would be more useful, and more realistic, if they had access to recordings of communicatively successful exchanges between non-native speakers.

An alternative source of spoken data is to use authentic material from, for example, radio or TV. Apart from the more formally scripted spoken texts, such as news broadcasts and documentary voice-overs, there is a lot of unscripted data, such as interviews, 'vox pop' segments (i.e. short interviews with a range of people about a particular topic, usually recorded in the Street), TV talk shows, and talk-back radio, and the relatively recent phenomenon of 'reality shows' (such as *Big Brother*)[4]. The main problems with this media material (apart from questions of Copyright) are, on the one hand, availability — it's not so easy to get hold of if one is teaching outside an English-speaking context — and, on the other, the level of 'insider' cultural knowledge that is necessary to make sense of such texts. Talk shows and reality shows are directed at a very specific audience and make no concessions to viewers who are not familiar with that context. Moreover, the conversations are often meandering, inconsequential, and highly colloquial. For most learners of English — especially of English as an International Language — such language is unlikely to provide a useful model. Here for example, is an extract, more or less taken at random, from Channel Four's popular reality show *Big Brother*.

Gos: Lisa, can I be rude?

Lisa: You want me to move?

Gos: You look better today.

Lisa: Than I did yesterday?

Gos: Yeah, definitely. I know you say about your make-up right, but I think you look a lot better without it.

Lisa: My boyfriend always says that.

Gos: It's true.

Lisa: I used it as a mask yesterday, literally. I overloaded.

Gos: Cameron said you looked really, really pretty without your make-up

and I'm like 'yeh, really pretty man - aiiiiiiii'. I like to throw in a red herring every now and again.

Steph: You causin' trouble Gos?

Lisa: Not at all. He's been very complimentary.

. Gos: I only picked up on it 'cos Cameron said.

Lisa. When I'm in here I probably won't wear any anyway.

Gos: Good. And give up smoking, you're killing me!

While the extract includes some useful interactive expressions *{Yeah, definitely. It's true. Not at all...}*, it also includes examples of fairly colloquial and idiomatic usage *{I'm like, yeah, really pretty, man ... I like to throw in a red herring now and again ...}*, plus references to shared knowledge, such as things that happened yesterday, as well as being about a topic that is probably only of interest to regular viewers (i.e. whether Lisa wears too much make, up or not).[5]

Using scripted data, in which natural speech is 'tidied up' or simulated such as in soap operas or extracts from films, can be a means of getting round the problem of unintelligibility. Some scriptwriters are better than others at capturing the characteristics of natural speech. Two researchers compared conversational openings and closings in both a New Zealand soap opera and coursebook dialogues, and came out in favour of the soap opera as being more representative of natural speech although still 'far from ideal'. The judicious choice of short extracts from such sources may be one way of supplementing coursebook material. But, as with other material on radio and TV, transcripts are seldom made available to the public, and this adds an extra chore for the teacher who wants to use them.

A compromise is to make our own recordings, using our teaching colleagues. For a start, teachers often have a well-developed sense of how to make adjustments to their speech that favour intelligibility without sacrificing authenticity. The following is a transcript of a recording a teacher made, minutes before a lesson, using teachers recruited from the staffroom, and with the instruction, 'Compliment Jackie on her earrings, and try to include an example of *ioh at a...* . Jackie, you respond, maybe saying where you got them'.

A: I really like your earrings. Where did you get them?

B: I got them in a little shop in Figueras, actually.

A: They really go with your outfit.

B: Cheers.

A: How much were they?

B: Three euros, I think.

A: Cor, what a bargain.

Notice that, although the language is kept within the bounds of comprehensibility of most intermediate learners, it still manages to include a number of features of spoken English, including the tails *actually* and *I think*, and the evaluative language *really*, *cheers*, and *cor*.

The recording is one thing, but the transcript is another. Coursebook recordings are now always accompanied by a transcription, which is usually located in a section at the back of the book. Making one's own transcript of a homemade recording can be a lengthy process, but there is no better way of getting to know the material and of discovering features that might initially have been overlooked. This is a powerful argument for getting the learners themselves to do the transcribing: it increases the chances of their noticing features of the data as well as helping develop their listening skills in general.

Linguists observe a number of conventions when making transcriptions of naturally-occurring talk, such as marking pause length and signalling overlaps (i.e. where two speakers are speaking at once). Most of this 'notation' will serve little pedagogic use, although, for some purposes, marking stressed words may be helpful. It is important, however, not to edit out too many of the performance effects, such as hesitations, repetitions, and false starts. Showing learners that even proficient speakers have to make real-time adjustments, and showing them *how* they make these adjustments, can only be helpful in the long run.

Whatever way the transcript is made, it is essential that a transcript be available for study purposes at some stage of the teaching sequence. No matter how many times learners are replayed a recording, there will be features of it that elude them until they see them written down. And even if they have reconstructed the text word for word, it will still be satisfying to match their mental representation of the text with the written form. Also, listening to the recording while at the same time reading it silently can help reinforce sound-spelling connections. Finally, it is often easier for the teacher to draw attention to patterns and regularities by reference to the written text than by simply trying to isolate them on a recording.

A basic procedure

Having obtained recorded data, how can the teacher put it to good practical use? There are a number of ways of using recorded speech data and their accompanying transcripts, but we can start with a basic procedure for staging the use of recordings. (Note that the use of the term *recording* below is shorthand for whatever form of recording is chosen, whether audiocassette, video, CD, DVD etc) [6]

Activate background knowledge - depending on the difficulty of the /V content, it may help to establish the topic and/or the context of the speech event: this will make the subsequent tasks easier. If, for example, the speakers on the recording are comparing two different models of bicycle, it will help the learners' listening load if they first brainstorm vocabulary related to bicycles (e.g. *tyres, gears, brakes, saddle, frame* etc). This both situates them, mentally, in terms of the topic and is a way of dealing with unfamiliar vocabulary items that are likely to occur. (The teacher can

introduce items that the learners don't come up with but which occur in the recording.) A related idea is to ask the learners to improvise a conversation on the same topic themselves, before playing them the recording.

Check gist - play the extract, or an initial segment of it, and ask general gist questions. For example, 'Who is talking to whom about what, and why?' Note that establishing the gist of what is going on is a prerequisite for all of the activities that follow. The advantages of video material in terms of providing contextual information should be obvious, but even video can't provide all the details, such as the topic of the conversation. Repeated listenings may be necessary, with learners noting key words and comparing in pairs or small groups, before a general consensus on the gist can be established.

Check register - related to the above, it is often important to establish *n* the register variables, particularly the tenor of the speech situation (see page 19), as these will have an impact on certain language choices, such as the degree of formality involved. Check, therefore, that the learners are clear as to the relationship between speakers, their relative rank, and/or social distance.

Check details — depending to what extent the teacher wants to achieve zero uncertainty — that is, 100% comprehension of the text on the part of all learners — the learners may need to be set further, more probing, tasks, such as a table to complete, a grid to fill, or multiple choice questions to answer. The recording should be replayed as many times as necessary for learners to complete these tasks. Learners should also be given the opportunity to consult each other.

Listen and read — hand out the transcript (assuming one is available; alternatively, learners can produce their own transcript at this stage, even if only of a part of the recording). Replay the recording while learners read silently.

Resolve doubts — learners should be given the opportunity to ask about any residual doubts or problems they have about the text. In a monolingual class, this may involve translating items that remain obscure or allowing learners to consult dictionaries.

Focus on language features — by now the learners should be sufficiently

familiar with the text to have a basis for 'guided noticing' of selected

features. This can involve the following procedures:

- *identifying*, e.g. underline, or circle, in the transcript examples of evaluative language.
- *counting*, e.g. count the number of times the speakers say *you know* and *I mean*.
- *classifying*, e.g. identify and classify the different discourse markers.
- *matching*, e.g. match idiomatic expressions in the text with their synonyms on a list.
- *connecting*, e.g. connect the pronouns in the text with their referents (i.e. the words they refer to).
- *comparing and contrasting*, e.g. compare these two versions of the same conversation and identify any differences.

An alternative way of guiding noticing is to provide a transcript that is

either incomplete or in some way different from the actual recording.

For example:

- Listen to the recording again and fill in the gaps in the transcript. (The gaps can represent all the discourse markers, for example.)

- Listen to the recording again and spot any differences in the transcript. (The difference could be that none of the backchannel devices (e.g. *uh-huh, really? how awful*) are included in the transcript.)[7]

The above procedure is not meant to be prescriptive and can be adapted according to the demands of the listening text itself, and to the level and needs of the learners. But one important principle should normally be observed: that learners need to have a basic understanding of the text before they embark on close study of its language features.

In this article we have looked at ways of raising learners awareness about features of speaking. This can be done through exposure to samples of speech that are;

- Audio-recorded
- Live, e.g. in the form of teacher-talk

Awareness can also be enhanced when learners notice the gap between what they can do and what a skilled practitioner can do. So far we have dealt with the issue of how to help learners fill gaps to their knowledge, with regard to speaking. But equally important is that the new-found knowledge is smoothly integrated into their existing language competence. That is, the knowledge needs to be appropriated so that it is available for use. To address this issue we will look at what we will call appropriation activities.

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